

Determination of Total Soil Nitrogen and Organic Carbon from Certain Infra-Red Peaks of IR-Curves of Soils

SHARAFAT ALI, P. C. SRIVASTAVA, O. P. SINGH and S. K. DE

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211002.

Manuscript received 14 February 1975; accepted 23 June 1975

Fifty soil samples from different regions of India have been collected and their infrared curves were observed by KBr-mull technique using Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer, 137. The depth (I/I_0) values of each infrared absorption peaks were calculated and correlated with the values of total soil nitrogen and carbon separately. Generally, Si-OH (bonded and unbonded water-peak), Si-OH (absorbed water-peak); Si-O (silica-peak); Si-H (pH-peak) and Si-C (carbon-peak) belonging to different infrared regions have been found to show their correlation (both positively or negatively) with the values of total soil N and C. Regression (straight line) equations were also obtained between the I/I_0 values and the N and C percent values, which may be used for routine analysis of these two soil constituents.

IN order to know the potential and kinetic fertility of the soil long and time consuming methods are already available. Rapid chemical methods with similar purpose are also given^{1,2}. However, the interpretation of IR-curves of soils from the point of view of determining their physico-chemical properties especially with reference to their total soil nitrogen and organic carbon, both qualitatively and quantitatively, will be entirely a new analytical method.

In this paper an attempt has been made to determine the total soil nitrogen and organic carbon by certain IR-peaks of fifty soil samples collected from different regions of India.

Experimental

Fifty soil samples have been collected from different parts of India from a depth of 0-20 cm (Table 1). The soils were dried, pulverised and passed through 100-mesh (British Standard) sieve. These soils were then chemically analysed for total soil nitrogen by Kjeldahl method² and organic carbon by Walkley and Black² method.

The infra-red curves of fifty soils were obtained by KBr-mull technique and the apparatus used was Perkin-Elmer Infra-red Spectrophotometer, model 137³. The IR-curves of each soil sample have been studied in the wavelength between 2.5μ to 15.0μ to which particular infra-red regions for the functional groups, Si-OH (bonded and unbonded water-peak, A); Si-OH (absorbed water-peak, B); Si-O (silica-peak, C); Al-O (alumina-peak, D); Si-H (pH-peak, E) and Si-C (carbon complex-peak, E) belong. Important absorption peaks have been allocated³ to particular functional groups and mentioned in Table 1.

The depth of IR-peaks (I/I_0) were calculated by baseline technique⁴. The average I/I_0 values for each functional group to which total soil nitrogen

and organic carbon values (in percent) were found to be significantly correlated have only been reported (Table 1) and discussed.

The coefficients of correlation and regression equations between I/I_0 values and the values of total soil nitrogen and carbon have also been reported in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Detail table showing the infrared absorption peaks values between 2.5μ to 15.0μ ⁵ belonging to different infrared curves of soils have been avoided to economise space, but, a comparative Table 1 showing the average I/I_0 values of infrared peaks in particular infrared regions (viz., Si-OH, Si-O, Si-H, Si-C functional groups) of the infrared curves of fifty soils have only been given.

The values of total organic carbon and nitrogen (%) were statistically correlated with the I/I_0 values (Table 1) of different peaks. It has been observed that IR-peaks belonging to Si-OH(A); Si-OH(B); Si-O(C); Si-H(E) and Si-C(F) infrared regions have significant correlations with N and C percentage. No significant correlation was obtained with Al-O(D) functional group (Table 2). Positive significant correlations have been obtained with Si-OH(A), Si-O(C) and Si-H(E) infrared absorption regions and organic carbon values. Generally, negative significant correlations between I/I_0 values belonging to Si-OH(A); Si-OH(B) and Si-C(F) infrared regions and nitrogen % values have been obtained. The Si-H(E) infrared region is found to have positive correlation with both of soil analyzates (N% and C% values).

The regression equations between I/I_0 values and the values of total organic carbon and nitrogen have been given in Table 2. The straight line equations so obtained with the nitrogen and carbon values

TABLE I—AVERAGE DEPTHS (1/I₀) OF INFRA-RED ABSORPTION PEAKS

Soil	FUNCTIONAL GROUPS						Soil Analyzatos	
	Si-OH (Bonded and Un- bonded water- peak) μ	Si-OH (Absorbed Water- peak) μ	Si-O (Silica peak) μ	Al-O (Alumina- peak) μ	Si-H (pH-peak) μ	Si-C (Carbon- peak) μ	Total %	Total %
	2.70- 3.500	4.2- 8.00	8.5- 9.50	10.95- 11.300	10.95- 11.300	12.0- 15.00	C	N
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Allahabad, U.P.	1.34	1.40	—	8.16	2.28	1.73	0.070	0.39
Almorah, "	1.55	1.24	7.00	11.36	1.77	1.15	0.080	0.89
Azamgarh "	1.30	1.25	2.80	4.00	2.00	1.19	0.030	0.44
Agra, "	1.22	1.15	1.55	2.32	1.08	1.25	0.020	0.37
Banda, "	1.39	1.25	3.14	4.79	1.72	1.48	0.080	0.59
Dehradun, "	1.29	1.11	1.83	2.71	1.32	1.08	0.090	0.71
Farukhabad "	1.64	1.29	3.85	8.64	2.76	1.12	0.050	0.48
Gorakhpur "	1.31	1.65	2.57	7.88	2.24	1.12	0.040	0.38
Lakhimpur Kheri, U.P.	1.26	1.14	2.29	3.39	1.48	1.15	0.390	1.30
Mirzapur "	1.55	1.20	2.57	7.00	1.85	1.20	0.050	0.49
Nainital "	1.48	1.23	2.08	16.00	2.40	1.48	0.060	0.41
Sultanpur "	1.15	1.18	2.14	2.91	1.60	1.16	0.030	0.47
Varanasi "	1.13	1.14	1.41	1.30	1.21	1.08	0.030	0.39
Jaunpur "	1.02	1.15	2.87	6.14	1.85	1.25	0.940	0.43
Ghazipur "	1.02	1.19	2.04	2.72	1.44	1.23	0.010	0.33
Jhansi "	1.66	1.27	2.55	8.50	1.35	1.15	0.925	0.49
Fatehpur "	1.37	1.24	2.70	4.93	1.35	1.21	0.021	0.43
Aligarh "	1.40	1.40	1.55	4.18	1.76	1.62	0.017	0.27
Munsoorie "	1.40	1.22	1.83	2.50	1.35	1.10	0.017	0.57
Barilly "	1.48	1.27	3.70	2.92	1.46	1.02	0.038	0.35
Dhanbad, Bihar	1.33	1.38	2.81	7.80	1.93	1.18	0.085	0.34
Ranchi "	1.47	1.31	3.59	5.36	1.76	1.15	0.066	0.65
Indore, M.P.	1.71	1.20	2.30	3.30	1.33	1.09	0.080	0.62
Shivapuri "	1.36	1.18	5.83	3.79	1.38	1.13	0.060	0.72
Palampur, H.P.	1.50	1.14	5.23	21.58	2.67	1.28	0.046	0.40
Chamba, "	1.21	1.18	2.51	4.18	1.50	1.11	0.035	0.55
Burdwan, W.B.	1.38	1.27	1.46	3.40	1.34	1.15	1.170	1.72
Calcutta, "	1.38	1.27	1.46	3.40	1.24	1.15	0.170	0.72
Darjeeling "	1.53	1.10	2.38	9.53	2.26	1.35	0.560	0.49
Koraput, Orissa	1.32	1.16	4.02	8.10	2.04	1.22	0.050	0.40
Mehsana, Gujarat	1.34	1.13	—	3.25	2.28	1.73	0.040	0.38
Dhulia, Maharashtra	2.09	1.26	4.00	13.00	1.50	1.12	0.039	0.40
Nander, "	2.08	1.25	—	8.50	1.50	1.12	0.060	0.45
Parbhani "	1.93	1.26	4.20	4.00	1.66	1.16	0.165	0.84
Poona "	1.27	1.16	2.75	5.14	1.68	1.19	0.080	0.83
Jalgaon "	1.49	1.18	3.28	2.05	1.19	1.04	0.070	0.46
Ratnagiri "	1.47	1.11	3.30	7.95	1.82	1.09	0.165	0.86
Nasik "	1.60	2.01	2.14	4.08	1.22	1.06	0.070	0.46
Godavari, A.P.	1.28	1.24	3.70	4.68	1.67	1.33	0.026	0.19
Guntur, "	1.62	1.16	—	7.00	1.41	1.05	0.130	0.42
Bangalore, Karnatak	1.39	1.32	2.29	4.06	1.66	1.10	0.120	1.59
Mandeya "	1.58	1.15	2.31	4.93	1.65	1.10	0.050	0.47
Sib-Sagar, Assam	1.12	1.14	1.46	2.05	1.12	1.16	0.104	1.47
Nawgaon "	1.19	1.15	2.08	3.85	1.43	1.10	0.050	0.43
Lakhimpur "	1.37	1.15	4.20	6.60	1.90	1.24	0.098	0.63
Jodhpur, Rajasthan	1.34	1.15	2.29	4.81	1.45	1.10	0.035	0.27
Nilgiris, Tamil-Nadu	1.38	1.20	—	3.45	1.18	1.06	0.065	0.60
Dharapuram, "	1.30	1.14	2.30	4.93	1.65	1.07	0.163	1.40
Goa	1.33	1.14	—	6.15	1.60	1.09	0.060	1.49
Kerala	1.45	1.00	3.50	6.15	1.60	1.08	0.056	0.48

TABLE 2—COEFFICIENTS OF CORRELATION (r -VALUE) AND STRAIGHT LINE EQUATIONS OBTAINED BETWEEN THE DEPTH OF INFRARED (I/I_0) PEAKS AND TOTAL NITROGEN AND CARBON % VALUES.

Infrared absorption region to be used for I/I_0 values	Coefficients of correlation ' r ' value		Straight line equations	
	Total N	Total C	Total N $Y =$	Total C $Y =$
Si-OH (Bonded and unbonded water-peaks)	-0.3225*	0.5749*	-0.61x+0.94	0.76x-0.50
Si-OH (Absorbed water-peak)	0.5714*	0.0189	-0.08x+0.47	0.02x+0.57
Si-O (Silica-peak)	0.0042	0.8275*	0.0001x+0.07	0.19x+0.14
Al-O (Alumina peak)	-0.0646	-0.1567	-0.0001x+0.07	0.00x+0.054
Si-H (pH-peak)	0.3373*	0.3754*	0.03x+0.02	-0.23x+0.37
Si-C (Carbon-peak)	-0.4900*	0.1561	-0.15x+0.25	0.34x+0.18

Note : 1. *Significant at 5% level of significance.

2. Y = Soil analyzates (in percent) and x = depth of infrared absorption peaks (I/I_0).

may be used for routine analysis of total nitrogen and organic carbon if the IR-curves of unknown soil samples and their different I/I_0 values as reported earlier are available. These equations will save much of time, labour and materials which are needed for the routine analysis of nitrogen and carbon (% values) of the soils used in the present experiment.

References

1. C. S. PIPER, "Soil and Plant Analysis", University of Adelaide, Australia, 1947.
2. S. K. DE, "Practical Agricultural Chemistry", Narayan Publishing House, Allahabad, 1965.
3. S. K. DE, D. Sc. Thesis, University of Allahabad, 1965.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis." ELBS and Longmans Green Co. Ltd., London, 1961.
5. SEARAFAT ALI, D.Sc. Thesis, University of Allahabad, 1974.